

Brian DuPree Real Estate discovered a lack of true client care within the existing real estate market. With that knowledge, Brian set out to join a business where client care came first and closing deals came second. Through these experiences, Brian is capable of providing a comprehensive investment approach to every transaction. He commands an understanding of the forces that drive value and will equip you to make the best possible decision. When you work with Brian DuPree Real Estate, you'll notice his responsiveness, patience and ability to explain each step of the process, backed by solid market analysis. As a 6th generation Georgian, Brian grew up in Athens and has deep connections to the city and its surrounding neighbourhoods.

Brian DuPree has a BA in Business from Georgia State University and is skilled Realtor with experience in residential, vacation home & investment real estate. Brian DuPree Real Estate has years of experiences and millions of sales under his belt. He know the stress that home buying and selling brings, but also believes it should be an exciting and rewarding experience. Brian DuPree Real Estate takes every opportunity to educate his clients as he walks them through the process together.

Brian DuPree Real Estate delivers results that exceed expectations and creates victories for his clients. Using his empathy and competitive nature, he advocates tirelessly for each of his clients to provide an extraordinary experience. When faced with complex challenges, Brian engages his creative drive to march a deal across the finish line. Brian DuPree Real Estate wants to become your real estate resource for life.